

Dehydrohalogenation of 1-Chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones

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Treatment of 1-chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones (1) with mild bases gives dehydrochlorinated products (4) and (or) (3) often accompanied by the reduced products (2).

Although literature abounds with examples of dehydrochlorination reactions involving C-chloro compounds, to our knowledge, such studies involving N-chloro compounds are much limited. We present herein the results of our investigation on the dehydrochlorination reactions of 1-chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones (1a-e)¹ catalysed by mild bases (strong bases decomposed the compounds). We tried the following two methods: (A) dehydrochlorination using sodium acetate in ethanol² and (B) dehydrochlorination using lithium carbonate in DMF³. In both cases the products were identified by the analysis of their ¹H nmr spectra.

Results and Discussion

Depending upon the nature of the reactants used and the method followed, dehydrochlorination of 1-chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones gave one or more of the following three types of products, namely, simple elimination products (3a-e), rearranged elimination products (4a-e) and reduction products (2a-e) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETAILS OF THE PRODUCTS OBTAINED IN DEHYDROCHLORINATION OF 1

Reactant	Product	Yield (%)		M.p.* °C
		Method A	Method B	
1a	4a	7	19	175-76
	2a	7	—	91-92
1b	4a	16	28	174-75
	3c	13	—	85-86
1c	4c	22	41	186-87
	2c	—	41	185-86
	3d	52	—	99-100
1d	4d	—	21	112-13
	2d	—	40	188-89
	3e	50	56	130-31

*4a, 4b, 4c, 2c and 2d were recrystallised from ethyl acetate and the rest from benzene-petroleum ether mixture.

1 ; X=Cl
2 ; X=H

3

4

a ; R¹=Me, R²=R³=H
b ; R¹=Et, R²=R³=H
c ; R¹=i-Pr, R²=R³=H
d ; R¹=R²=Me, R³=H
e ; R¹=R²=Me, R³=H

A perusal of Table 1 indicates the following, (i) while method A gave all the three types of products were obtained in method B, (ii) in both the methods, reactant 1e gave only the reduction product and no elimination products, (iii) in the two cases where simple elimination products were obtained, the formation of double bond took place between nitrogen and that carbon which has no vicinal alkyl substituent, and (iv) in all the cases where rearranged elimination products were obtained, the double bond was formed between the benzylic carbon and the unsubstituted ketomethylene carbon.

Mechanism of reaction: As the chlorine linked to nitrogen and neither of the vicinal hydrogen atoms are in the *anti*-periplanar or *syn*-periplanar orientations¹, the operation of E2 mechanism is highly unlikely. The possibility of E1 mechanism

TABLE 2—¹H NMR AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	δ (CDCl ₃ ; TMS)				Others	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹
	H(2)	H(3)	H(5)	H(6)		
2a	3.50 (d, <i>J</i> 11 Hz)	2.40–2.80 (m, H(3), H(5))		3.90 (dd, <i>J</i> 11, 5 Hz)	0.80 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, C(3) CH ₃), 2.00 (1H, bs, NH), 7.10–7.30 (10H, m, ArH)	3 300(NH), 1 700 (C=O)
2c	3.40 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	2.35–2.75 (m, H(3), H(5))		3.80 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 5 Hz)	0.90 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₃ (i-Pr)), 1.20 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₃ (i-Pr)), 1.90 (1H, bs, NH), 7.10–7.40 (m, ArH)	3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O)
2d	3.35(s)	—	2.5(m)	3.70(m)	0.65 (3H, s, C(3)CH ₃), 1.20 (3H, s, C(5)CH ₃), 1.95 (1H, bs, NH), 7.20–7.40 (10H, m, ArH)	3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O)
2e	3.50 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	2.70(m)	same as H(3)	same as H(3)	0.90 (6H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, C(3) CH ₃ , C(5) CH ₃), 1.90 (1H, bs, NH), 7.10–7.40 (10H, m, ArH)	3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O)
3c	—	2.80 (d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz) 3.00 (d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz)	1.80–2.30 (2H, m, H(5), CH(i-Pr))	4.10 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	0.90 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz), CH ₃ (i-Pr), 1.10 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₃ (i-Pr)), 6.90–7.20 (10H, m, ArH)	1 700 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N)
3d	—	2.98 (d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz) 3.00 (d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz)	—	4.15(s)	0.64 (3H, s, C(5) CH ₃), 1.31 (3H, s, C(5)CH ₃), 7.20–7.50 (10H, m, ArH)	1 725 (C=O), 1 380 (C=N)
4a	—	4.90(s)	2.80(s)	4.30 (d, <i>J</i> 11 Hz)	1.00 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, C(5) CH ₃), 1.50 (1H, s, NH), 7.10–7.40 (10H, m, ArH)	3 240 (NH), 1 615 (C=O), 1 580 (H=C)
4b	—	5.20(s)	2.50(s)	4.50 (d, <i>J</i> 11 Hz)	0.90 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.60 (3H, m, NH, CH ₂ CH ₃), 6.40–7.20 (10H, m, ArH)	3 200 (NH), 1 600 (C=O), 1 580 (C=C)
4c	—	5.10(s)	2.30(m)	4.70(m)	0.95 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₃ (i-Pr)), 1.15 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₃ (i-Pr)), 1.60 (1H, s, NH), 2.10 (1H, m, CH (i-Pr)), 7.30 (10H, m, ArH)	3 215 (NH), 1 560 (C=O), 1 580 (C=C)
4d	—	5.10(s)	—	4.70(s)	0.70 (3H, s, C(5)CH ₃), 1.35 (3H, s, C(5)CH ₃), 7.30 (10H, m, ArH)	3 225 (NH), 1 620 (C=O), 1 600 (C=O)

is excluded on the grounds of poor leaving ability of Cl⁻ group and poor stability of nitrenium ion. Thus, we are left with ElcB as the only alternative mechanism. Further, the operation of ElcB mechanism will be facilitated by the presence of the fairly acidic benzylic protons and the relatively good stability of benzylic carbanions. Of the two alpha-hydrogens flanking the carbonyl group, the one attached to the non-alkylated carbon is more acidic (an alkyl group is electron releasing and hence acid weakening) and hence more prone to attack by base. This explains the formation of 3 having double bond between the benzylic carbon and nitrogen. A hydrogen shift in 3 forms 4 more stabilised by extended conjugation. The exclusive formation of rearranged elimination products in method B is probably due to the higher dielectric constant of DMF.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer. Brockmann grade neutral alumina was used for column chromatography.

General procedure for the dehydrochlorination of 1 by method A: A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), sodium acetate (0.03 mol) and ethanol (250 ml) was kept stirring at ambient temperature for about 50 h. After filtering out the precipitated sodium chloride and stripping off the solvent ethanol, the residue was diluted with ice-water and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried (sodium sulphate) and the solvent removed (rotary

flash evaporation). The resulting products were separated (column) and recrystallised.

General procedure for the dehydrochlorination of 1 by method B: A mixture of 1 (0.005 mol), lithium carbonate (0.025 mol) and DMF (70 ml) was kept stirring under reflux (100°) for about 15 h. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and filtered. After repeated washings, the

residue was dried, chromatographed and the separated products were recrystallised.

References

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